

Functional Near Infrared Spectroscopy

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In this document, I briefly introduce the theory behind the measurement of haemoglobin (Hb) concentration in the human frontal cortex by functional near infrared spectroscopy (fNIRS) and I apply it to a consumer-grade wearable (Athena S Muse). In particular, I describe a script in R programming language that derives resting-state relative concentrations of both oxygenated and non-oxygenated Hb from five-minute recordings. I briefly discuss the results of my 9-month recordings and their correlation with a subjective measure of cognitive functioning.

1	The Beer-Bouguer-Lambert law	- 1 -
2	Hemoglobin concentration	- 2 -
3	Athena S Muse.....	- 5 -
4	A longitudinal study.....	- 8 -
5	The script.....	- 9 -
6	References	- 14 -

1 The Beer-Bouguer-Lambert law

We define radiation *intensity* as the radiative energy passing through an area per unit solid angle, per unit of area projected normal to the direction of passage, and per unit time. Intensity is measured in $\frac{J}{s \cdot m}$. We also say that intensity is *spectral* if it is characterized by a specific wavelength λ . We indicate a spectral intensity with the symbol $I(\lambda)$. Let us now consider a spectral intensity $I(\lambda)$ incident normally on a volume of thickness dx , we can write

$$\text{Eq. 1} \quad I(\lambda, x + dx) - I(\lambda, x) = \frac{\partial I(\lambda, x)}{\partial x} dx + o(dx)$$

Because of scattering and absorption of the material within the volume, there must be a loss of energy (*extinction*), therefore $\frac{\partial I(\lambda, x)}{\partial x} < 0$. The extinction is assumed to be proportional to the incident energy, according to a positive coefficient

$$\text{Eq. 2} \quad K = K(\lambda, x, [C_1], [C_2], \dots, [C_n])$$

called *extinction* coefficient, where $[C_i]$ is the concentration of the i^{th} component of the volume invested by the intensity. Molecules that interacts with light by absorption and scattering are usually called *chromophores*. In other words, we assume that

$$\text{Eq. 3} \quad \frac{\partial I(\lambda, x)}{\partial x} = -KI(\lambda, x)$$

and by integration over x we have

$$\int_{x_1}^{x_2} \frac{\frac{\partial I(\lambda, \xi)}{\partial \xi}}{I(\lambda, \xi)} d\xi = \int_{x_1}^{x_2} K d\xi \Rightarrow$$

$$\text{Eq. 4} \quad \ln \frac{I(\lambda, x_2)}{I(\lambda, x_1)} = - \int_{x_1}^{x_2} K d\xi \Leftrightarrow I(\lambda, x_2) = I(\lambda, x_1) e^{-\int_{x_1}^{x_2} K d\xi}$$

This relationship is named after Pierre Bouguer (1698-1758) but it is sometimes attributed to Lambert and Beer. In this document, we will call it the Beer-Lambert law, in agreement with the literature about near infrared spectroscopy in living tissues. In particular, if the extinction coefficient is constant along the path followed by the intensity, we have the simplified expression

$$\text{Eq. 5} \quad I(\lambda, x_2) = I(\lambda, x_1) e^{-K(x_2-x_1)}$$

The integral $\int_{x_1}^{x_2} K d\xi$ goes under the name of *attenuation* (A), therefore we have

$$\text{Eq. 6} \quad A = \ln \frac{I(\lambda, x_1)}{I(\lambda, x_2)} = \int_{x_1}^{x_2} K(\lambda, x, [C_1], \dots) d\xi$$

It must be specified here that attenuation is often expressed as *optical density* (OD), and this generates confusion because there is a different convention for the base of the logarithms. In particular, we have

$$\text{Eq. 7} \quad OD = \log_{10} \frac{I(\lambda, x_1)}{I(\lambda, x_2)} = \frac{\ln \frac{I(\lambda, x_1)}{I(\lambda, x_2)}}{\ln 10} = 0.43A$$

The extinction coefficient has two components, one for absorption and one for scattering, and can be expressed as:

$$\text{Eq. 8} \quad K(\lambda, x, [C_1], [C_2], \dots, [C_n]) = \sum_{i=1}^n (\alpha_i(\lambda, x) + \sigma_i(\lambda, x)) [C_i]$$

where we have introduced coefficients of absorption α_i and of scattering σ_i . Therefore, if we consider a medium with extinction coefficient that is independent from x , the attenuation is given by

$$\text{Eq. 9} \quad A = (x_2 - x_1) \sum_{i=1}^n (\alpha_i(\lambda) + \sigma_i(\lambda)) [C_i]$$

where we have plugged Eq. 8 into Eq. 6.

2 Hemoglobin concentration

When we evaluate extinction of intensity through living tissue, we see that above 1300 *nm* water absorbs all photons over a pathlength of less than a few millimetres, while below 700 *nm* haemoglobin absorption and substantial scattering cause high attenuation. In the 700-1300 *nm* range however (near infrared), intensity can travel a significant distance across living tissues, as documented by Jöbsis in 1977 [2] on animals. In the adult human brain, the loss in optical density is about 2 OD per centimetre at a wavelength of 1060 *nm*, according to figure 3.C of [3], and it is much higher (about 1.5 OD per millimetre) at wavelength of 514 *nm*, according to the same source. A chromophore of great interest in neurosciences is haemoglobin in both its oxygenated form (HbO_2) and de-oxygenated form (Hb), because it is only present in the red blood cell, and its oxygenation state reflects blood oxygenation. Let us now write Eq. 9 for haemoglobin under the hypothesis of negligible scattering:

$$A(x, \lambda) = x(\alpha_{Hb}(\lambda)[Hb] + \alpha_{HbO_2}(\lambda)[HbO_2])$$

where we have assumed – to simplify the notation – that $x_1 = 0, x_2 = x$. Let us now say that the concentration of the two chromophores change under two different measures (for activation of the brain tissue for instance), we can write the change in attenuation as follows:

$$\text{Eq. 10} \quad \Delta A(x, \lambda) = x(\alpha_{Hb}(\lambda)\Delta[Hb] + \alpha_{HbO_2}(\lambda)\Delta[HbO_2])$$

On the other hand, it must be

$$\Delta A(x, \lambda) = \ln \frac{I(\lambda, 0)}{I'(\lambda, x)} - \ln \frac{I(\lambda, 0)}{I(\lambda, x)} = \ln \frac{I(\lambda, 0)}{I'(\lambda, x)} \frac{I(\lambda, x)}{I(\lambda, 0)} \Rightarrow$$

$$\text{Eq. 11} \quad \Delta A(x, \lambda) = \ln \frac{I(\lambda, x)}{I'(\lambda, x)}$$

where $I'(\lambda, x)$ and $I(\lambda, x)$ are detected intensities at the receiver, in two different measures. The measurement of the change in attenuation eliminates the need for the knowledge of the intensity of the emitter. We are interested in using Eq. 10 and Eq. 11 to derive the changes in concentration of the two forms of haemoglobin, therefore we need two equations. If we have two sources of intensity at two different wavelengths λ_1, λ_2 we have the linear system

$$\text{Eq. 12} \quad \begin{cases} \Delta A(x_{\lambda_1}, \lambda_1) = x_{\lambda_1}(\alpha_{Hb}(\lambda_1)\Delta[Hb] + \alpha_{HbO_2}(\lambda_1)\Delta[HbO_2]) \\ \Delta A(x_{\lambda_2}, \lambda_2) = x_{\lambda_2}(\alpha_{Hb}(\lambda_2)\Delta[Hb] + \alpha_{HbO_2}(\lambda_2)\Delta[HbO_2]) \end{cases}$$

which in matrix form can be written:

$$\text{Eq. 13} \quad \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_{Hb}(\lambda_1) & \alpha_{HbO_2}(\lambda_1) \\ \alpha_{Hb}(\lambda_2) & \alpha_{HbO_2}(\lambda_2) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \Delta[Hb] \\ \Delta[HbO_2] \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_{\lambda_1}^{-1}\Delta A(x_{\lambda_1}, \lambda_1) \\ x_{\lambda_2}^{-1}\Delta A(x_{\lambda_2}, \lambda_2) \end{bmatrix}$$

The solution is

$$\text{Eq. 14} \quad \begin{bmatrix} \Delta[Hb] \\ \Delta[HbO_2] \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_{Hb}(\lambda_1) & \alpha_{HbO_2}(\lambda_1) \\ \alpha_{Hb}(\lambda_2) & \alpha_{HbO_2}(\lambda_2) \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} x_{\lambda_1}^{-1}\Delta A(x_{\lambda_1}, \lambda_1) \\ x_{\lambda_2}^{-1}\Delta A(x_{\lambda_2}, \lambda_2) \end{bmatrix}$$

The inversion of the square matrix is straightforward:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \alpha_{Hb}(\lambda_1) & \alpha_{HbO_2}(\lambda_1) \\ \alpha_{Hb}(\lambda_2) & \alpha_{HbO_2}(\lambda_2) \end{bmatrix}^{-1} = \frac{1}{\alpha_{Hb}(\lambda_1)\alpha_{HbO_2}(\lambda_2) - \alpha_{Hb}(\lambda_2)\alpha_{HbO_2}(\lambda_1)} \begin{bmatrix} \alpha_{HbO_2}(\lambda_2) & -\alpha_{HbO_2}(\lambda_1) \\ -\alpha_{Hb}(\lambda_2) & \alpha_{Hb}(\lambda_1) \end{bmatrix}$$

In conclusion, the solutions of Eq. 12 are

$$\text{Eq. 15} \quad \Delta[HbO_2] = \frac{\frac{\alpha_{Hb}(\lambda_1)\Delta A(x_{\lambda_2}, \lambda_2)}{x_{\lambda_2}} - \frac{\alpha_{Hb}(\lambda_2)\Delta A(x_{\lambda_1}, \lambda_1)}{x_{\lambda_1}}}{\alpha_{Hb}(\lambda_1)\alpha_{HbO_2}(\lambda_2) - \alpha_{Hb}(\lambda_2)\alpha_{HbO_2}(\lambda_1)}$$

$$\text{Eq. 16} \quad \Delta[Hb] = \frac{\frac{\alpha_{HbO_2}(\lambda_1)\Delta A(x_{\lambda_2},\lambda_2)}{x_{\lambda_2}} - \frac{\alpha_{HbO_2}(\lambda_2)\Delta A(x_{\lambda_1},\lambda_1)}{x_{\lambda_1}}}{\alpha_{Hb}(\lambda_2)\alpha_{HbO_2}(\lambda_1) - \alpha_{Hb}(\lambda_1)\alpha_{HbO_2}(\lambda_2)}$$

with $\Delta A(x_{\lambda_i}, \lambda_i) = \ln \frac{I(\lambda_i, x_{\lambda_i})}{I'(\lambda_i, x_{\lambda_i})}$ (Eq. 11). For the human brain, where the source of photons and the receiver are placed on the scalp a few centimetres apart, it has been proposed to express the path of the light as

$$\text{Eq. 17} \quad x_{\lambda} = L \cdot DPF(\lambda, age)$$

where DPF (differential path length factor) is a correction to the distance between source and receiver (L) expressed as a function of age and wavelength (λ):

$$\text{Eq. 18} \quad DPF(\lambda, age) = \alpha + \beta age^{\gamma} + \delta 10^{-7} \lambda^3 + \epsilon \lambda^2 + \zeta \lambda$$

for the frontal human head, with $\alpha = 223.3, \beta = 0.05624, \gamma = 0.8493, \delta = -5.723 \cdot 10^{-7}, \epsilon = 0.001245, \zeta = -0.9025$, according to [4]. Note that DPF has no dimensions.

The values for $\alpha_{Hb}(\lambda)$ and $\alpha_{HbO_2}(\lambda)$ have been tabulated by Scott Prahl and available on line [5]. To plug these values in Eq. 15 and Eq. 16, they must be multiplied by $\ln 10 = 2.303$, because they follow the convention of the optical density (see Eq. 7). They are expressed in $(\text{cm} \cdot \frac{\text{mole}}{\text{liter}})^{-1}$ and this means that the path between source and receiver must be expressed in centimeters and that the concentrations will be given in moles per liter (and can be converted easily into gram per liter by multiplication of the molecular weight of the species). The values of $\alpha_{Hb}(\lambda)$ and $\alpha_{HbO_2}(\lambda)$ are plotted in log scale in Figure 1, using the script below.

Figure 1. Values of $\alpha_{Hb}(\lambda)$ and $\alpha_{HbO_2}(\lambda)$ in log scale for the wavelength between 250 and 1000 nm, expressed in $\frac{1}{\text{cm} \cdot \frac{\text{mole}}{\text{liter}}}$

```
# file name: extinction
#
# year: 2026
# month: 06
# day: 13
#
#-----
# It plots coefficient of absorption for Hb and HbO2 in 1/(cm*mole/liter)
# Data are from: https://omlc.org/spectra/hemoglobin/summary.html
#-----
#
# read data
```

```

#
mydata<-fread("extinction.txt")
#
# convert from optical density to attenuation
#
mydata$Hb<-mydata$Hb*log(10,base=exp(1))
mydata$Hb02<-mydata$Hb02*log(10,base=exp(1))
#
# plot
#
jpeg("Absorbtion.JPG",quality=100,res=100,width=1500,height=500)
minX<-min(mydata$lambda)
maxX<-max(mydata$lambda)
minY<-log10(min(mydata$Hb,mydata$Hb02))
maxY<-log10(max(mydata$Hb,mydata$Hb02))
#
plot(mydata$lambda,log10(mydata$Hb),type="l",lty=1,xlab="lambda (nm)",
      ylab="1/(cm*mole/liter)",
      xlim=c(minX,maxX),ylim=c(minY,maxY),lwd=2)
par(new=T)
plot(mydata$lambda,log10(mydata$Hb02),type="l",lty=2,xlab="",ylab="",
      xlim=c(minX,maxX),ylim=c(minY,maxY),lwd=2)
legend("topright",legend=c("log10(alpha_Hb)","log10(alpha_Hb02)"),lty=c(1,2),lwd=c(2,2))
dev.off()

```

3 Athena S Muse

We now adapt the results of paragraph 2 to a specific device: Athena S Muse. This device has one source at the center of the forehead and two receivers per side. The source emits three wavelengths: 660, 730, and 850 nm. Also, ambient light is measured for each sensor. Raw data recorded by the Mind Monitor App are provided in 16 channels, as specified below. In the table I also indicated the distance between the emitter and the four receivers.

	660 nm Ch	730 nm Ch	850 nm Ch	Ambient	Path (cm)
Left Outer	9	1	3	11	3
Left Inner	13	5	7	15	1
Right Inner	14	6	8	16	1
Right Outer	10	2	4	12	3

First, we derive mean values for each channel, for each recording. Next, to correct for ambient light and red light (660 nm) which is reflected mainly from the scalp, we can use a linear regression model. For instance, if we consider the intensity reaching the left outer sensor at 730 nm (Ch 1), we consider the model

$$\text{Eq. 19} \quad I_{730}^{LO} \sim \beta_0 + \beta_1 I_{660}^{LO} + \beta_2 I_{ambient}^{LO}$$

and then we substitute intensity I_{730}^{LO} with the residual of the regression. We repeat the same regression for the all the receivers, for both the wavelengths, for a total of eight regressions. These regressions will be performed over the time series of mean daily values. The need for this correction seems obvious from Figure 2. To overcome the problem of negative values and zero values (which

would cause division by zero when calculating attenuation), we can scale the results, for instance between 1 and 2.

Figure 2. Regressions between the received intensities at 730 and 850 *nm* and both red and ambient light, for the left inner receiver (channel 1) in a five-minute recording.

Then we proceed with the derivation of haemoglobin concentrations using Eq. 14. The calculation of the paths for each pair receiver/wavelength using Eq. 18 is straightforward. We first define a function for DPF:

```
DPF_func<-function(lambda,age) {
  #
  alpha<-223.3
  beta<-0.05624
  gamma<-0.8493
  delta<--5.723*10^(-7)
  epsilon<-0.001245
  zeta<-0.9025
  #
  DPF<-alpha + beta*age^gamma + delta*lambda^3 + epsilon*lambda^2 + zeta*lambda
  return(DPF)
}
```

We then store the corrected paths in a data.frame:

```
mypath<-data.frame(L.Outer.730=3*DPF_func(730,age),
  R.Outer.730=3*DPF_func(730,age),
  L.Outer.850=3*DPF_func(850,age),
  R.Outer.850=3*DPF_func(850,age),
```

```
L.Inner.730=1*DPF_func(730,age),
R.Inner.730=1*DPF_func(730,age),
L.Inner.850=1*DPF_func(850,age),
R.Inner.850=1*DPF_func(850,age)
```

Also, the matrix of the linear system in Eq. 13 can be easily built in R:

```
alpha<-function(C,lambda) {
  if (C=="Hb02"&lambda==730) a<-log(10)*390
  if (C=="Hb"&lambda==730) a<-log(10)*1102.2
  if (C=="Hb02"&lambda==850) a<-log(10)*1058
  if (C=="Hb"&lambda==850) a<-log(10)*691.32
  return(a)
}
#
lambda_1<-730
lambda_2<-850
alpha_mat<-matrix(c(alpha("Hb",lambda_1),alpha("Hb",lambda_2),
                    alpha("Hb02",lambda_1),alpha("Hb02",lambda_2)),nrow=2,ncol=2)
rownames(alpha_mat)<-c(lambda_1,lambda_2)
colnames(alpha_mat)<-c("Hb","Hb02")
```

For the calculation of the relative attenuation, we can use the mean values for each pair receiver/wavelength, across all the measurements, assuming that all the measurements are performed in the same conditions (resting state, for instance). Even easier is the use of an arbitrary value (for instance 2, which is the maximum intensity, if we scaled intensities between 1 and 2).

Figure 3. Relative concentrations of Hb and Hb02 (normalized) for my left frontal lobe. Resting-state measures were taken daily under the same conditions, for a period of nine months. Moving mean of 15 days.

4 A longitudinal study

A time series of nine months for the left frontal lobe (resting state, five-minute recordings) is plotted in Figure 3. During the months of daily five-minute recordings with Muse S Athena, I also recorded several Heart Rate Variability parameters using a Polar band (as described in [6]), finger SpO2, body temperature, and a three-level subjective score (a measure of cognitive functioning), collected three times per day and then averaged (the higher the better I am). I also collected and analysed EEG data, using the same Athena S Muse, for AF7 (left frontal) and AF8 (right frontal). Then I computed a correlation table, using the Spearman method, with a threshold for significance of 0.05 (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Relative concentrations of Hb and Hb02 (normalized) for my left frontal lobe and their correlations with time not-away from keyboard. Pearson correlation, threshold for significance of 0.05. Moving means over 5 days, with non-overlapping windows (to reduce autocorrelation).

What emerges is that my subjective score (Score_m) negatively correlates with total haemoglobin concentration (particularly in the left frontal lobe). In turns, haemoglobin concentration positively correlates with EEG power in the alpha waves. In conclusion, the worse my subjective score is, the higher the blood in my frontal lobes, and the more the brain slows to alpha waves. Note that the subjective score, is a measure of cognitive functioning.

5 The script

The complete function to the analysis of resting state fNIRS from the output of the app Mind Monitor (not zipped, 16 channels) for the Athena S Muse band is reported below along with two other functions, called by it, to manage timestamp and to plot Figure 2. It is assumed that the readings are placed in a folder called EEG.

```
#
#-----
# Convert human readable date (HRD) into Unix epoch (or Unix time or POSIX time or
# Unix timestamp). It works on multiple HRD formats.
#-----
#
epoch<-function(date,format) {
  date<-as.character(date)
  #
  # Define possible date formats
  #
  if (format=="MDY") {
    formats <- c("%m/%d/%Y %H:%M:%S", "%m/%d/%Y", "%m-%d-%Y %H:%M:%S", "%m-%d-%Y")
  } else if (format=="DMY") {
    formats <- c("%d/%m/%Y %H:%M:%S", "%d/%m/%Y", "%d-%m-%Y %H:%M:%S", "%d-%m-%Y")
  } else if (format=="YDM") {
    formats <- c("%Y/%d/%m %H:%M:%S", "%Y/%d/%m", "%Y-%d-%m %H:%M:%S", "%Y-%d-%m")
  } else if (format=="YMD") {
    formats <- c("%Y/%m/%d %H:%M:%S", "%Y/%m/%d", "%Y-%m-%d %H:%M:%S", "%Y-%m-%d")
  } else {
    stop("date format not supported")
  }
  #
  # Try each format until one works
  #
  for (fmt in formats) {
    EPC <- try(as.POSIXct(date,format=fmt,tz = "UTC"),silent=TRUE)
    if (!is.na(EPC)) return(as.numeric(EPC))
  }
  #
#-----
# It plots readings of intensities for each receiver/wavelength for a session provided as input
#-----
#
fNIRS_plot<-function(recording) {
  #
  # Generate a plot for each receiver with regressions between readings and red
  # and ambient light, for both wavelengths
  #
  for (ch in c(1,5,6,2)) {
    #
    if (ch==1) receiver<-"Left Outer"
```

```

if (ch==5) receiver<-"Left Inner"
if (ch==6) receiver<-"Right Inner"
if (ch==2) receiver<-"Right Outer"
#
col<-ch+1
figure.name<-paste(receiver, ".JPG")
jpeg(figure.name,quality=100,res=100,width=750,height=500)
par(mfrow=c(2,2))
#
# Red - 730 nm
#
Xmin<-min(recording[[col+8]],na.rm=T)
Xmax<-max(recording[[col+8]],na.rm=T)
Ymin<-min(recording[[col+0]],na.rm=T)
Ymax<-max(recording[[col+0]],na.rm=T)
model<-lm(formula = recording[[col+0]] ~ recording[[col+8]])
plot(recording[[col+8]],recording[[col+0]],xlab="Red Intensity",
      ylab=paste("Intensity",receiver,"730 nm"),
      xlim=c(Xmin,Xmax),ylim=c(Ymin,Ymax),
      col="black")
abline(model,lwd=2,col="red")
#
# Red - 850 nm
#
Xmin<-min(recording[[col+8]],na.rm=T)
Xmax<-max(recording[[col+8]],na.rm=T)
Ymin<-min(recording[[col+2]],na.rm=T)
Ymax<-max(recording[[col+2]],na.rm=T)
model<-lm(formula = recording[[col+2]] ~ recording[[col+8]])
plot(recording[[col+8]],recording[[col+2]],xlab="Red Intensity",
      ylab=paste("Intensity",receiver,"850 nm"),
      xlim=c(Xmin,Xmax),ylim=c(Ymin,Ymax),
      col="black")
abline(model,lwd=2,col="red")
#
# Ambient - 730 nm
#
Xmin<-min(recording[[col+10]],na.rm=T)
Xmax<-max(recording[[col+10]],na.rm=T)
Ymin<-min(recording[[col+0]],na.rm=T)
Ymax<-max(recording[[col+0]],na.rm=T)
model<-lm(formula = recording[[col+0]] ~ recording[[col+10]])
plot(recording[[col+10]],recording[[col+0]],xlab="Ambient Intensity",
      ylab=paste("Intensity",receiver,"730 nm"),
      xlim=c(Xmin,Xmax),ylim=c(Ymin,Ymax),
      col="black")
abline(model,lwd=2,col="red")
#
# Ambient - 850 nm
#
Xmin<-min(recording[[col+10]],na.rm=T)
Xmax<-max(recording[[col+10]],na.rm=T)
Ymin<-min(recording[[col+2]],na.rm=T)
Ymax<-max(recording[[col+2]],na.rm=T)
model<-lm(formula = recording[[col+2]] ~ recording[[col+10]])
plot(recording[[col+10]],recording[[col+2]],xlab="Ambient Intensity",
      ylab=paste("Intensity",receiver,"850 nm"),

```

```

    xlim=c(Xmin,Xmax),ylim=c(Ymin,Ymax),
    col="black")
abline(model,lwd=2,col="red")
#
dev.off()
}
}
#
#-----
# It calculates relative concentration of Hb and HbO2 for each receiver. The baseline is built
# using mean values over all the recordings
#-----
#
fNIRS_func<-function(year) {
#
# Read
#
current_dir<-getwd()
sub_dir<-"EEG"
folder_path<-file.path(current_dir,sub_dir)
file_names<-list.files(folder_path)
days<-length(file_names)
#
# For each file, if uncompressed, compress it
#
for (i in 1:days) {
  if (!grepl(".gz",file_names[i])) {
    temp<-read.csv(file.path(folder_path,file_names[i]),header=T,sep=",")
    file.remove(file.path(folder_path,file_names[i]))
    file_names[i]<-paste0(file_names[i],".gz")
    fwrite(temp,file.path(folder_path,file_names[i]))
  }
}
#
# Store each recording in a list, only readings before 'hour_co' and only one for day
#
hour_co<-16
fNIRS.data<-list()
k<-1
for (i in 1:days) {
  day<-substr(file_names[i],13,22)
  hour<-substr(file_names[i],25,26)
  if (as.numeric(hour)<hour_co) {
    if (!day%in%names(fNIRS.data)) { # only one reading for day
      temp<-fread(file.path(folder_path,file_names[i]),header=T,sep=",")
      test<-sum(temp$Optics9,na.rm=T)
      name<-substr(temp$TimeStamp[1],1,10) # name is the date as YYYY-MM-DD
      if (test>0) {
        temp<-temp[,c("TimeStamp",paste0("Optics",1:16))] # only optical data
        fNIRS.data[[k]]<-temp
        names(fNIRS.data)[k]<-name
        k<-k+1
      }
    }
  }
}
days<-length(fNIRS.data)

```

```

#
# Plot readings for one of the recordings
#
# fNIRS_plot(fNIRS.data[[1]])
#
# Save daily mean values for each channel
#
mymeans<-data.frame(matrix(NA, nrow=days, ncol=ncol(fNIRS.data[[1]]))
colnames(mymean)<-colnames(fNIRS.data[[1]])
colnames(mymean)[1]<-"date"
#
for (i in 1:days) {
  mymeans$date[i] <- epoch(names(fNIRS.data)[i], "YMD")
  for (j in 2:ncol(mymean)) {
    mymeans[[j]][i] <- mean(fNIRS.data[[i]][[j]], na.rm=T)
  }
}
#
# Prepare a data frame with the readings, one row per day
#
v<-rep(NA,days)
mydata<-data.frame(L.Outer.730=v,R.Outer.730=v,L.Outer.850=v,R.Outer.850=v,
  L.Inner.730=v,R.Inner.730=v,L.Inner.850=v,R.Inner.850=v,
  date=mymean$date)
#
# Derive values for each day after correction for ambient and red light at each
# receiver across the time series
#
for (ch in c(1,5,6,2)) {
  #
  col<-ch+1
  #
  # 730 nm
  #
  model<-lm(formula = mymean[[col+0]] ~ mymean[[col+8]]+mymean[[col+10]])
  mydata[,ch]<-model$residuals
  #
  # 850 nm
  #
  model<-lm(formula = mymean[[col+2]] ~ mymean[[col+8]]+mymean[[col+10]])
  mydata[,ch+2]<-model$residuals
}
remove(fNIRS.data)
#
# Scale results between 1 and 2 (to avoid division by zero)
#
for (j in 1:8) {
  mydata[,j]<-rescale(mydata[,j],to=c(1,2))
}
#
# Derive differential path factor and paths for each receiver/wavelength
#
DPF_func<-function(lambda,age) {
  #
  alpha<-223.3
  beta<-0.05624
  gamma<-0.8493
}

```

```

delta<--5.723*10^(-7)
epsilon<-0.001245
zeta<--0.9025
#
DPF<-alpha + beta*age^gamma + delta*lambda^3 + epsilon*lambda^2 + zeta*lambda
return(DPF)
}
#
# Store the absorption coefficients (1/(cm*mole/liter)) in a matrix
#
alpha<-function(C,lambda) {
  if (C=="Hb02"&lambda==730) a<-log(10)*390
  if (C=="Hb"&lambda==730) a<-log(10)*1102.2
  if (C=="Hb02"&lambda==850) a<-log(10)*1058
  if (C=="Hb"&lambda==850) a<-log(10)*691.32
  return(a)
}
#
lambda_1<-730
lambda_2<-850
alpha_mat<-matrix(c(alpha("Hb",lambda_1),alpha("Hb",lambda_2),
                    alpha("Hb02",lambda_1),alpha("Hb02",lambda_2)),nrow=2,ncol=2)
rownames(alpha_mat)<-c(lambda_1,lambda_2)
colnames(alpha_mat)<-c("Hb","Hb02")
#
# Prepare a data frame for the concentrations of Hb and Hb02
#
myconc<-data.frame(L.Outer.Hb=v,R.Outer.Hb=v,L.Outer.Hb02=v,R.Outer.Hb02=v,
                  L.Inner.Hb=v,R.Inner.Hb=v,L.Inner.Hb02=v,R.Inner.Hb02=v,
                  date=v)
#
# Store concentrations
#
for (i in 1:days) {
  age<-as.numeric(substr(HRD(mydata$date[i]),1,4))-year
  for (ch in c(1,5,6,2)) {
    #
    # Calculate concentrations for channel ch
    #
    mypath<-data.frame(L.Outer.730=3*DPF_func(730,age),
                      R.Outer.730=3*DPF_func(730,age),
                      L.Outer.850=3*DPF_func(850,age),
                      R.Outer.850=3*DPF_func(850,age),
                      L.Inner.730=1*DPF_func(730,age),
                      R.Inner.730=1*DPF_func(730,age),
                      L.Inner.850=1*DPF_func(850,age),
                      R.Inner.850=1*DPF_func(850,age))
    #
    x.lambda.1<-mypath[,ch] # path for lambda 1 (730 nm)
    x.lambda.2<-mypath[,ch+2] # path for lambda 2 (850 nm)
    #
    # We use as reference I = 2 (corresponding to the highest intensity at the receiver = lowest concentration)
    #
    delta.A.1<-log(2/mydata[i,ch]) # change in attenuation for lambda 1 (730 nm)
    delta.A.2<-log(2/mydata[i,ch+2]) # change in attenuation for lambda 2 (850 nm)
    #
    vector<-matrix(c(delta.A.1/x.lambda.1,delta.A.2/x.lambda.2),nrow=2,ncol=1)
  }
}

```

```

#
delta.conc<-solve(alpha_mat,vector)
rownames(delta.conc)<-c("delta.Hb","delta.HbO2")
#
# Store results
#
myconc$date[i]<-mydata$date[i] # day
myconc[i,ch]<-delta.conc[1,1]
myconc[i,(ch+2)]<-delta.conc[2,1]
}
}
#
# Add [HbTot] for each receiver
#
myconc$L.Outer.HbTot<-myconc$L.Outer.Hb + myconc$L.Outer.HbO2
myconc$L.Inner.HbTot<-myconc$L.Inner.Hb + myconc$L.Inner.HbO2
myconc$R.Outer.HbTot<-myconc$R.Outer.Hb + myconc$R.Outer.HbO2
myconc$R.Inner.HbTot<-myconc$R.Inner.Hb + myconc$R.Inner.HbO2
#
# Results
#
return(myconc)
}

```

6 References

For the derivation of the Beer-Lambert law, I followed paragraph 12-4 of [1]. One of the first studies about the feasibility of NIRS in brain tissue is [2], to my knowledge. Detailed experimental data on the extinction of optical density in the adult human brain were first reported in [3]. The empirical formula for DPF (Eq. 18) was published in [4]. Experimental data for $\alpha_{Hb}(\lambda)$ and $\alpha_{HbO_2}(\lambda)$ in the range $250 \leq \lambda \leq 1000$ are collected by Scott Prahl in [5].

1. Siegel R and Howell JR, *Thermal Radiation Heat Transfer*, 3rd edition, HPC, 1992
2. Jöbsis FF, *Noninvasive, Infrared Monitoring of Cerebral and Myocardial Oxygen Sufficiency and Circulatory Parameters*, Science, Vol. 198, 1977
3. Svaasand LO and Ellingsen R, *Optical Properties of Human Brain*, Photochemistry and Photobiology, Vol. 38, 1983
4. Scholkmann F and Wolf M, *General equation for the differential pathlength factor of the frontal human head depending on wavelength and age*. J. Bio. Opt., 2013
5. <https://omlc.org/spectra/hemoglobin/summary.html>
6. Maccallini, P. (2024). Introduction to the analysis of heart rate variability from 5-minute recordings. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20177290>